

AGGRESSIVE AND SELF-INJURIOUS BEHAVIORS OF INTELLECTUALLY CHALLENGED ADULTS: TWO CASE STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

This study endeavors to explore the aggressive and self-injurious behaviors of intellectually challenged adults. Case study method has been adopted and BASIC-MR (Part-B) was used for collection of relevant data from the subjects. Results show that female client shows more aggressive behaviors and male client shows more self-injurious behaviors. Results of the data has been analyzed and presented on the basis of international research studies. A strong theoretical discussion has been done on the basis of established research worker's views. Further in-depth qualitative and quantitative research with a strong theoretical discussion is recommended.

Keywords: Intellectually challenged, Aggressive behaviors, Self-injurious behaviors.

INTRODUCTION

With increasing population in India, the numbers of intellectually challenged individuals are also growing. The prevalence of intellectually challenged individuals in the overall population of India is 10.5 cases/1000, with 10.08/1000 in rural and 11/1000 in the urban population (Lakhan, Ekundayo & Shahbazi, 2015). Challenging behaviors are very common among the people with intellectually challenged individuals. Usually, challenged children show more behavioral problems than non-disabled children (Farth, Platt & Parson, 2017), particularly who are intellectually challenged/visually challenged/autistic/hyperactive/multiple challenged children. The major causes of problem behaviors among those developmentally challenged children are different but, in most cases, they show such type of behaviours as they are unable to draw stimulations from the external environment. So, they become habituated in different types of self-stimulatory behaviours, among the ten different dimensions of problem behaviors as prescribed and published by NIMH (Secunderabad) and developed by Peshawaria and Venkatesan

(1992). Among the problem behaviours the most dangerous behaviours are self-injurious and aggressive behaviours. Aggressive and self-injurious behaviours are most harmful for both, to the child as well as the family.

In the study of Crocker and Others (2006), it was noted that intellectually challenged adults showed different types of aggressive behaviors. Davies and Oliver (2015) found that intellectually challenged people are habituated in aggressive behaviors. They also noted that range of aggressive behaviors are not same among all the intellectually challenged individuals. Bowring, Totsika, Hestings, Toogood and Griffith (2016) also found that individuals' with severe intellectually challenged show different types of aggressive behaviors.

McClintock, Holl and Oliver (2003) reported that self-injurious behaviours are more common among severe and profound intellectually challenged individuals. Children with autism spectrum disorder also show both aggressive as well as self-injurious behaviours other than noncompliance and stereotyped behaviors (Maston & Marie, 2007). Dev, Thomas and Bright (2001) concluded that severe intellectually challenged individuals are unable to make successful communication which causes their behavioral problems, like self-injurious behaviors. Eymen and Call (1977) from their survey concluded that aggressive behaviors are common among intellectually challenged individuals. Studies of Jacobson (1982), Harris (1993), Tyres (2006), Kishore, Nizamie and Nizamie (2005) and Lundqvist (2013), supported the study of Eymen and Call (1977).

From a series of study conducted by Nanda (1995, 1998, 1999, 2004), Nanda and Das (2005), Nanda and Mitra (2006), it was found that intellectually challenged and visually challenged individuals showed different types of behavioral problems such as aggressive and self-injurious behaviors.

Therefore, the present investigations after a long review of related literatures selected the present research question, whether aggressive and self-injurious behaviours are present among the center based intellectually challenged adults?

METHODOLOGY

This is a case study method, in which the researchers have studied two adults (The age of the male participant is 23 and the age of female participant is 32) with intellectually challenged who are living in a residential care home for intellectually challenged, which is located at Sonarpur, West Bengal, India. The researchers observed them on daily basis

(except national holidays and Sundays) for three months (from January to March, 2020) and they also have taken written consent from their caretakers of the home.

Subjects

The researcher has selected two subjects (case 1 and case 2) purposively for the present study.

Tool

Behavioral Assessment Scales for Indian Children with Mental Retardation (BASIC-MR) Part-B was used in this study to assess the problem behaviors among the adults with intellectually challenged. This scale is suitable for intellectually challenged between the age of 3-16 (18) years. But it can be used for adult individuals with intellectually challenged. This scale has total 75 items grouped under 10 domains: violent and destructive behaviors, temper tantrums, misbehaves with others, self-injurious behaviors, repetitive behaviors, odd behaviors, hyperactivity, rebellious behaviors, antisocial behaviors and fears. Each item of the scale has three-point rating scale, viz, never (n), occasionally (o), and frequently (f). If the stated problem behavior presently does not occur in the subject, mark 'never' and give a score of 'zero'. If the stated problem behaviour presently occurs once in a while or now and then, it is marked 'occasionally' and give a score of 'one'. If the stated problem behavior presently occurs quite often or habitually, is marked 'frequently' and give a score of 'two'. The maximum possible score for subject on this scale is 150 (Peshawaria & Venkatesan, 1992).

A demographic data sheet was also used to cover queries on personal details, type and degree of disability, family background etc.

Case studies

Case - 1

The first client is a woman having aggressive behaviors of different degree. The client is 32 years old and is a resident of a home for the intellectually challenged persons. During birth, she had low birth weight and pre-mature baby in eight months of pregnancy. She was kept in an incubator in a govt. hospital. During her childhood, it was recognized by her parents that she had developmental problems. She never went to a special school nor to any early intervention center. When her age was 15, she got admission in the present home and for last 17 years, she has been staying in this home. She never went to her

original residence. Her parents are less interested about this client and do not bear any responsibility of their daughter. She is speechless and shows different types of aggressive behaviors to other home mates as well as to her care giver. In every month during her menstruation, she become more aggressive. She is interested to touch and hug when she found any male individuals in her close contact. Except biting others and attacking and pocking others with weapons, she occasionally shows different types of violent and destructive behaviors. She never got any supports such as speech therapy, occupational therapy and behaviour therapy. She lives alone in her own world.

Case -2

The second case is a severe intellectually challenged man. He is 23 years old. He has one brother, who is intellectually normal. During his birth, he had late birth cry and the body was bluish in color. From his birth, he had shown a feeding problem. The parents were not educated and therefore, they thought that he will develop normally when he will be grown up. In about 3-4 years of age, they first detect that their child is not normal. They visited a special school and came to know that their child is not normal. After 8-9 years of training in the special school, they admitted their baby in the present home for the intellectually challenged and mentally ill people. The client is unable to engage himself in any kind of productive and creative work. The institution has no facilities of behavior therapy, occupational therapy and speech rehabilitation. The client shows different types of self-injurious behaviors whose apparent reason is unknown to the present investigator as well as the institution authority. For day and night, he remains alone and shows problem behaviors.

RESULT

The results are presented in the following table

Dimensions	Items	Frequency of problems behaviours	
		Case:1	Case:2
Violent and destructive behaviours	1Kicks others	o	n
	2. Pushes others	o	n
	3Pinches others	o	n
	4. Pulls hair, ear, body parts of others	o	n
	5. Slaps others	o	n
	6. Hits others	o	n

	7. Spites on others	o	n
	8. Bangs objects	o	o
	9. Slams doors	o	o
	10. Bites others	n	n
	11. Attacks or pokes others with weapon (blade, stick, pencil)	n	n
	12. Throws objects at others	o	n
	13. Tears/pulls threads from own or others clothing	o	n
	14. Tears up own or others books, papers, magazines	o	n
	15. Breaks objects/glass/toys	n	o
	16. Damages furniture	o	o

Self-injurious behaviours	1. Bangs head	n	f
	2. Bites self	n	n
	3. Cuts or mutilates self	n	f
	4. Pulls own hair	n	n
	5. Scratches self	n	f
	6. Hits self	n	f
	7. Puts objects into eyes/nose/ear	n	n
	8. Eats inedible things	n	n
	9. Peels skin/wounds	f	f
	10. Bites nails	n	n

(0= Occasionally, n= Never, f= Frequently)

DISCUSSION

According to BASIC-MR (Part-B) aggressive behaviors that are violent and destructive behaviors are of 16 types that is why in this scale 16 items of violent and destructive behaviors are included. Case - 1 is a women client with intellectual impairment and shows all the 13 items of violent and destructive behaviors out of 16 items. All these 13 items of problem behaviors, she shows occasionally.

In the study of Bouras and Drummond (1992), it was found that out of all different types of problem behaviors, violent and destructive behaviors were present among 33.3% clients. According to them, aggressive behaviors towards others were more common

among the intellectually challenged individuals. They also noted that aggressive behaviors were more common among severely and profoundly intellectually challenged. This finding is consistent with the previous studies of Easton and Menolascino (1982). It was noted that (Bouras and Drummond,1992) aggressive behaviors found occasionally among mild intellectually challenged persons but Benson (1985), Menolascino (1988), Iverson and Fox (1989) found higher level of aggressive behaviors more often among severely intellectually challenged individuals. According to Eaton and Menolascino (1982), presence of aggressive behaviors among intellectually challenged is highly individualistic, and might be present as behavioral problems (Reiss, 1985). According to Gold and others (1989), aggressive behaviors can be included under the group of psychiatric disorder. Due to the presence of problematic behaviors like aggression among the intellectually challenged individuals, their integration in the home, family, local community is problematic as well as they cannot develop a relationship with people without disability (Mansell et. al.,1987). Therefore, they need skill development and rehabilitation practitioners must emphasis on it. So, support staff, therapist and professionals must be capable of meeting the social and educational needs of people with intellectual disability.

In the present study, the client never bites others even when she became violent and destructive. On the other hand, Bowring, Totsika, Hastings, Toogood and Griffith (2016). noticed that 2.3% intellectually challenged sample shows biting behaviors to others. In their study, 8.3% sample possess aggressive and destructive behaviours.

Case - 2 is a male individual having severe intellectual disability. He shows self-injurious behaviors like, head banging, self-cutting, self-scratching, self-hitting and peeling his skin or wounded himself and he showed all these problematic behaviors frequently. He never bites himself or shows other self-injurious behaviors like, hair pulling, putting objects into eyes, nose, ear, never eat inedible things and never showed nail biting behaviors. Bouras and Drummond (1992) on the other hand noticed that, self-injurious behaviors are more common in women, not in men. In the study of Bowring et. al. (2016), it was noted that 7.5% sample shows different types of self-injurious behaviors and those self-injurious behaviors have a significant negative impact on quality of life. They noticed that a strong association is present between lack of day time engagement and self-injurious behaviors. The challenged individual who engages himself in self-injurious behaviors, they cannot engage themselves in other day time activities. The same view was established in the study of Lowe, Allen, Jones, Brophy, Moore (2007).

In the study of Emerson and Bromley (1995), it was noted that most severe group of intellectually challenged shows either self-injurious behaviors or aggression (43%) as

their main challenging behaviors. Sometimes, self-injurious behaviors noticed to occur together with biting, head hitting, scratching, pinching, body hitting and hair pulling. They also found that the occurrence of self-injurious behaviors tends not to be related to other types of problem behaviors. It means that self-injurious behaviors may not coexist with other types of problem behaviors. Therefore, these people have no greater risk than other people with other types of challenging behaviors which coexist together.

In the study of Holden and Gitlisen (2003), it was found that self-injurious behaviors shown by 55% of intellectually challenged learners. They noticed that severely and profoundly retarded shows more self-injurious behaviors compared to mild and moderately challenged individuals. They noticed that food refusal is more common in person with severe and profound intellectually challenged and the individual showing self-injurious behaviors demonstrate increased appetite.

CONCLUSION

Problem behaviors like, aggressive and destructive behaviors, self-injurious behaviors are common among the severe intellectually individuals. It is more common in the individual who is unable to communicate with others. Speech therapy and behavior therapy are very much important for this group of people. Family, Community and the State should know the problems of the intellectually challenged, its etiologies and probable mode of interventions. Maintaining a good mental health for this group of people is most important. Regular sensitization training program is needed for the family of this group of people.

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